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Evolution of shear zones through the brittle-ductile transition: The Calamita Schists (Elba Island, Italy)

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Abstract

A network of shear zones that evolved through the brittle-ductile transition is exposed in the Calamita Schists, Elba Island, Italy. The shear zones formed during Late Miocene contractional deformation coeval with high grade contact metamorphism (~650 °C) related to the emplacement of plutonic rocks at shallow crustal levels (~7-10 Km). An early stage high metamorphic grade foliation was overprinted by mylonitic deformation that progressively localized on low-metamorphic grade shear bands producing S-C mylonites during cooling of contact aureole. Localization of deformation on shear bands was driven by temperature decrease that triggered strain partitioning between 'hard' high grade relics and 'soft' shear bands. Softening of shear bands occurred likely due to fluid influx and retrograde growth of fine-grained phyllosilicates. The interconnection of anastomosing shear bands and passive rotation of the relic high grade foliation caused widening of the shear bands producing mylonites with a composite mylonitic foliation and C' shear bands. An estimate of the vorticity number W_k of the flow of ~0.3 – 0.5 was obtained from the orientation of C' shear bands measured at the meso- and thin section-scale. Close to the brittle-ductile transition, the growth of soft phyllosilicates allowed C' shear bands to act as precursory structures to brittle deformation localized into an array of low-angle faults and shear fractures.

1. Introduction

Shear zones are tabular high-strain zones localized within domains of relatively lower strain that accommodate deformation in the lithosphere (Ramsay and Graham, 1970; Sibson, 1977; Ramsay, 1980; Lister and Snoke, 1984). They are usually distinguished in plastic (ductile or viscous) or brittle shear zones, according to their dominant deformation mechanism (Fossen and Cavalcante, 2017). However, brittle and ductile deformation mechanisms interplay during deformation, accompanying nucleation, growth and evolution of shear zones (e.g. Fousseis et al., 2006; Pennacchioni and Mancktelow, 2007; Fousseis and Handy, 2008). The transition from brittle to ductile behaviour differs from mineral to mineral and depends in first order on the temperature of

45 deformation (Sibson, 1983; Hirth and Tullis, 1994; Gleason and Tullis, 1995). Temperature is also
46 the critical parameter that controls dislocation creep regimes (Hirth and Tullis, 1992; Stipp et al.,
47 2002), as well as fluid reactivity and metamorphic reactions (Bucher and Grapes, 2011). At high
48 grade ($T > 600$ °C), only unusual dry conditions (Jackson et al., 2004; Gerald et al., 2006; Menegon
49 et al., 2011) or high strain rates (e.g. Gleason and Tullis, 1995) enhance rock strength favouring
50 brittle deformation, like in the case of pseudotachylites reported in the lower crust (Austrheim and
51 Boundy, 1994; Menegon et al., 2017). In the vast majority of cases, high-temperature shear zones
52 are dominated by crystal plastic deformation, with silicates, like quartz and feldspars, forming
53 elongate ‘ribbon grains’ that define the foliation (White et al., 1980; Gapais, 1989; Hippertt et al.,
54 2001; Rosenberg and Stünitz, 2003). Moreover, under high temperature conditions, the average
55 grain size tends to be coarse as dynamic recrystallization occurs by grain boundary migration (Stipp
56 et al., 2002). Strain partitioning is quite uncommon, as large rock volumes deform by low flow
57 stress and therefore high grade shear zones tend to be thick and characterized by a continuous
58 mesoscale foliation (Passchier and Coelho, 2006).

59 At medium to low grade (300 °C $< T < 600$ °C), shear zones exhibit a more complex behaviour.
60 Competency contrasts between different lithologies becomes important and results in heterogeneous
61 deformation of rocks with strain partitioning between rheologically ‘strong’ and ‘weak’ domains
62 (Passchier and Coelho, 2006). Some minerals (e.g. quartz) deform by dislocation creep while others
63 (e.g. feldspar) may undergo brittle fracturing or deform by grain size sensitive mechanisms (e.g.
64 Tullis et al., 1982; Menegon et al., 2013; Viegas et al., 2016). As a consequence, shearing localizes
65 and produces complex arrays of shear zones (Pennacchioni, 2005; Fousseis et al., 2006; Carreras et
66 al., 2010) that bounds volumes of relatively low-strain (lozenges; Ponce et al., 2013). Shear zones
67 themselves show internal strain partitioning highlighted by the presence of shear band structures
68 (Berthé et al., 1979) that localize shearing obliquely to the co-existing mylonitic foliation (S). Shear
69 bands are distinguished in relatively straight and continuous C shear bands, elongated parallel to the
70 shear zone boundary, and short and closely spaced at the mm- to the cm-scale C’ shear bands that

71 develop obliquely in respect to the shear zone boundary (Berthé et al., 1979; White, 1979; Lister
72 and Snoke, 1984), alternatively known as extensional crenulation cleavage (Platt and Vissers,
73 1980). Conjugate sets of C' shear bands with opposite sense of shear, synthetic and antithetic
74 respectively, may sometimes be developed in response to the bulk shear zone flow (Law et al.,
75 2004; Little et al., 2011; Gillam et al., 2014). Deformation in shear zones is characterized by a
76 strong grain size reduction, which has itself been regarded as an efficient strain softening
77 mechanism (White et al., 1980; Kilian et al., 2011; Platt, 2015). The formation of a lattice preferred
78 orientation, allowing slip on the 'softer' slip system (Rutter et al., 2001; Ji et al., 2004) or
79 substitution of 'strong' phases with a mixture of 'soft' grains by metamorphic reaction (Steffen et
80 al., 2001; Stünitz and Tullis, 2001), also contribute to keep deformation localized within discrete
81 shear zones at low- to medium grade conditions. As the offset and strain increase, shear zone
82 thicken at the expenses of low-strain domains (Means, 1995). This has been documented in several
83 natural examples (e.g. Tauern window: Pennacchioni and Mancktelow, 2007; Cap de Creus: Füsseis
84 et al., 2006) and related to the linkage of several shear zone segments that cut through the wall rock.
85 Strain hardening of the shear zone core (caused by the growth of 'strong' phases, the accumulation
86 of dislocations or softening of the walls) commonly occurs promoting widening of shear zones
87 (Fossen and Cavalcante, 2017).

88 Especially at low-grade conditions (i.e. shallow crustal levels), slight changes in temperature may
89 cause swings in deformation mechanisms and influence how deformation is partitioned within the
90 shear zone. An example is represented by the Glarus thrust in the Swiss Alps, that developed at
91 shallow crustal levels accommodating over 50 Km of displacement and localizing deformation in
92 ~1 metre of mylonites. During thrust activity, temperature decrease led to a narrowing of the shear
93 zone in the fault core with the later development of brittle cataclastic bands parallel to the shear
94 zone walls (Ebert et al., 2007). In the South Armorican Shear Zone, one of the major tectonic
95 lineaments of the Variscan chain, shearing produced mylonites with shear bands (Berthé et al.,
96 1979). Bukovská et al. (2016) showed that, while the main mylonitic foliation formed at around

97 ~550 °C, shear bands developed at ~300-350 °C. These authors also documented the progressive
98 widening of shear bands, aided by microcracking that promotes fluid infiltration and reaction
99 softening. As a result deformation progressively localizes on shear bands that are oblique to the
100 mylonitic foliation. The importance of strain partitioning at the brittle/ductile transition may indeed
101 dramatically increase as brittle structures are superimposed onto a pre-existing ductile fabric. Brittle
102 structures may localize parallel to the shear zone walls, as in the case of the Glarus thrust (Ebert et
103 al., 2007) or take advantage of precursory shear bands and oblique structures nucleating in unlikely
104 orientations in respect to the typical ‘Andersonian’ faults of Anderson (1951). Failure along pre-
105 existing foliations has been documented in several metamorphic units (Butler et al., 2008;
106 Massironi et al., 2011; Bistacchi et al., 2012) and related to the low-friction coefficient of ‘weak’
107 phyllosilicates aligned on foliations (Zhang and He, 2016).

108 In this study we present a detailed meso- and microscale analysis of shear zones, evolved from
109 ductile to brittle conditions within the high- to medium- metamorphic grade Calamita Schists in
110 southeastern Elba Island (Italy). Shearing in the Calamita Schists has been imposed by contractional
111 tectonics, coeval with pluton emplacement at very shallow (< 7 Km) crustal level (e.g., Papeschi et
112 al., 2017). The transition from high-temperature to low-temperature deformation has been
113 determined by the relatively rapid (< 1 Ma) cooling of the metamorphic rocks hosting the
114 monzogranite (Musumeci and Vaselli, 2012). We highlight the role of shear bands in localizing
115 deformation from high-temperature to low-temperature conditions and in promoting the switch to
116 the brittle regime, where shear bands have acted as ductile precursors for brittle, non-Andersonian
117 faults.

118

119 **2. Geological setting**

120 In the northern Tyrrhenian Sea, Elba Island exposes a complete structural section of the hinterland
121 sector of the northern Apennines belt (Boccaletti et al., 1971) that recorded early to late Miocene

122 nappe stacking and late Miocene contractional deformation coeval with emplacement of intrusive
123 rocks (Pertusati et al., 1993; Keller and Coward, 1996; Massa et al., 2017).

124 The Elba Island nappe stack consists of non-metamorphic and metamorphic tectonic units (Keller
125 and Coward, 1996) separated by a major thrust fault (Capo Norsini thrust; CNT in Fig. 1), into an
126 Upper and a Lower Complex (Musumeci and Vaselli, 2012). The Upper Complex is characterized
127 by non-metamorphic ocean-derived units on top of very low-grade continental units (see Massa et
128 al., 2017 for a detailed description). The Lower Complex consists of two continent-derived
129 metamorphic units, the Ortano Unit and the underlying Calamita Unit, which are characterized by
130 Paleozoic metasediments and metavolcanics (Musumeci et al., 2011) and Mesozoic age siliciclastic
131 and carbonate metasediments (Fig. 1).

132 The Lower Complex features early Miocene blueschist to greenschist facies metamorphism (Bianco
133 et al., 2015), which has been deeply overprinted by late Miocene low-pressure/high-temperature
134 (LP/HT) metamorphism in the amphibole to pyroxene hornfels facies (Musumeci and Vaselli,
135 2012), dated between 6.7 and 6.2 Ma (Musumeci et al., 2011, 2015). Peak metamorphic conditions
136 in the Lower Complex exceeded 650 °C at pressures below 0.18-0.20 GPa (Duranti et al., 1992).
137 LP/HT metamorphism has been related to the emplacement of the Porto Azzurro pluton, which is
138 buried at ~150-200 metres beneath the Calamita peninsula (Musumeci et al., 2015) and exposed
139 only as scattered outcrops of monzogranite (Fig. 1). Furthermore, tourmaline-bearing leucogranite
140 and pegmatite dykes (Eastern Elba dyke complex; Mazzarini and Musumeci, 2008) widely crop out
141 in the eastern sector of the Calamita peninsula (Fig. 1). Available radiometric ages of the
142 outcropping magmatic products range between 6.33 ± 0.07 Ma (leucogranite dyke; Musumeci et al.,
143 2015) and 5.9 ± 0.2 Ma (monzogranite; Maineri et al., 2003).

144 Pluton emplacement and LP/HT related metamorphism were coeval with late Miocene regional
145 scale east-verging shortening, testified by (i) thrust shear zones (Calanchiole shear zone and
146 Felciaio shear zone; CSZ and FSZ in Fig.1; Musumeci and Vaselli, 2012) and (ii) a kilometre-scale

147 upright antiform of foliation (Ripalte antiform; Fig. 1), cored by high-grade metamorphic rocks and
148 leucogranites (Mazzarini et al., 2011).

149 All the tectonic structures of the nappe stack and the late Miocene intrusive rocks in the Lower
150 complex, were crosscut by the Zuccale fault (ZF in Fig. 1; Collettini and Holdsworth, 2004; Smith
151 et al., 2011; Musumeci et al., 2015), whose activity postdated igneous rocks emplacement and
152 cooling. Debate involves the interpretation of the ZF as a detachment or a thrust (see discussion in
153 Musumeci et al., 2015). According to the former interpretation, the ZF would represent the main
154 extensional structure, while according to the latter interpretation, the ZF would constitute the roof
155 thrust of a large scale late Miocene duplex structure affecting the whole eastern Elba nappe stack
156 (see Fig. 13 in Papeschi et al., 2017).

157

158 **3. The Calamita Unit**

159 *3.1. Metamorphism and structural setting*

160 The Calamita Unit, host of the Porto Azzurro pluton (Fig. 1), consists of interlayered schists and
161 metapsammities of Early Carboniferous age (Calamita Schists Fm.) overlain by Triassic
162 metasiliciclastics (Barabarca quartzite Fm.) and metacarbonates (Calanchiole marble Fm.).
163 Andalusite + cordierite + K-feldspar + biotite ± white mica in the Calamita Schists and diopside +
164 tremolite assemblages in the Calanchiole marble indicate temperatures between 500 and 600 °C
165 (Musumeci and Vaselli, 2012) with peak metamorphic conditions exceeding 650 °C at pressures
166 below 0.18-0.20 GPa (Duranti et al., 1992). At map scale, the peak metamorphic assemblage allows
167 to distinguish a white mica + biotite + cordierite + andalusite zone on the western side of the
168 Calamita peninsula and a biotite + K-feldspar + cordierite + andalusite zone on the eastern side.
169 Common retrograde phases include white mica, sericite and chlorite.

170 The Calamita Schists are characterized by localized high-strain domains (HSDs), developed during
171 Late Miocene deformation and heterogeneously distributed at map scale, that display a continuous
172 foliation associated with shear bands (Papeschi et al., 2017). HSDs are characterized by: i) N-S

173 striking and moderately (10-40°) W-dipping foliation, ii) E-W trending stretching and mineralogical
174 lineations, iii) constant top to the east/northeast sense of shear and iv) east-verging low angle brittle
175 faults that cross cut the main schistosity (0-15° eastward dip). At the microscale, quartz fabric in
176 HSDs outlines an evolution of deformation mechanisms from grain boundary migration to bulging
177 recrystallization that has been interpreted as indicative of progressive temperature decrease during
178 deformation (Papeschi et al., 2017).

179 In the following paragraphs we focus on the meso- and microscale fabric of HSDs, investigated in
180 two different sections, namely (i) the Capo Calvo HSD (Fig. 2a) and (ii) the Praticciolo HSD (Fig.
181 4a), that are characterized by different fabrics and located on the eastern and western limb of the
182 Ripalte antiform respectively (location in Fig. 1). Details about the samples investigated in these
183 sections are provided in Appendix A.

184

185 **4. High temperature ductile fabric: Capo Calvo section**

186 *4.1. Mesostructures*

187 At Capo Calvo, the Calamita Schists crop out as high metamorphic grade metapsammites (biotite +
188 andalusite + cordierite + K-feldspar) intruded by leucogranite and pegmatite dykes (Fig. 2a).

189 The dominant mesoscale fabric is a high grade metamorphic foliation (Sp) that strikes N140-160
190 and dips moderately (20-50°) to the northeast (Fig. 2a). Mineral lineations are defined by
191 aggregates of quartz and biotite and by the preferred orientation of andalusite, cordierite and K-
192 feldspar: they trend about N050-N090 and plunge to the northeast (Fig. 2a).

193 The Sp is defined by alternations of well foliated biotite-rich and stretched quartz-rich layers that
194 wrap around weakly foliated biotite-andalusite-cordierite-bearing lozenges, whose asymmetric
195 shape is consistent with top to the east sense of shear (Fig. 2b). The Sp is cross cut at low angle (20-
196 30°) by top to the east C and C' shear bands (Fig. 2b) defining an S/C fabric in which the Sp
197 corresponds to the oblique S foliation (Fig. 2b). C shear bands dip moderately (20 - 50°; Fig. 2a)
198 towards the east and are characterized by thickness from few millimetres up to some centimetres

199 and spacing ranging from several centimetres up to some decimetres. C' shear bands are
200 characterized by steep eastward dip (between 40 and 80°; Fig. 2a) and make an angle of ~10-15°
201 with C shear bands. They are discontinuous and characterized by millimetric thickness and a
202 spacing of several centimetres.

203 C shear bands, defined by thin, stretched micaceous and quartzitic layers, form an array of
204 interconnected medium- to fine-grained shear planes with areas of linkage and wrap centimetric to
205 millimetric lozenges with an oblique S foliation (Fig. 2b). In the most strained domains, C shear
206 bands evolve in a well developed mylonitic foliation (Sm) characterized by subparallel quartz- and
207 mica-rich layers enveloping boudinated andalusite-cordierite-biotite pods (Fig. 2c). The Sp foliation
208 in the walls is dragged into parallelism with the Sm, consistently with top to the east sense of shear.
209 Steeply east dipping top to the east C' shear bands with centimetric spacing cross-cut the Sm (Fig.
210 2c).

212 4.2. *Microstructures*

213 At the microscale, the main foliation (Sp) is defined by alternations of millimetric quartz ribbons
214 and thin biotite-rich layers or elongated quartz grains with trails of biotite (Fig. 3a). The Sp wraps
215 lenses of diablastic aggregates characterized by intergrown coarse -grained (500 μm – 2 mm)
216 euhedral andalusite and cordierite, commonly altered in fine-grained sericite, biotite and K-feldspar
217 with poikiloblastic biotite inclusions (Fig. 3b).

218 Quartz occurs as coarse (~500 μm) grains showing interlobate to amoeboid grain boundaries with
219 island grains (Jessel, 1987) and patchy undulose extinction. When associated to other phases,
220 commonly biotite, pinning microstructures (Passchier and Trouw, 2005), indicative of fast grain
221 boundary migration (e.g. Stipp et al., 2002, 2010), are common (Fig. 3a). Finer quartz grains (<100
222 μm) with ellipsoidal shape occur as bulges along grain boundaries, showing roughly the same size
223 as coarse quartz grains subgrains.

224 At the contact with C shear bands, the oblique Sp foliation consists of quartz ribbons and
225 lepidoblastic coarse-grained biotite bands (Fig. 3d) that wrap coarse-grained (up to 5 mm) diablastic
226 aggregates of biotite, K-feldspar, andalusite and cordierite. Coarse quartz grains display undulose
227 extinction and are mantled by fine-grained (10-100 μm) interlobate quartz aggregates (Fig. 3d).
228 Biotite shows kinks and wide extinction bands that are roughly perpendicular to the basal cleavage
229 planes. Sericite ribbons, elongated parallel to the Sp foliation, wrap porphyroclast of andalusite,
230 cordierite and K-feldspar.

231 The transition between the Sp foliation and C shear bands (Fig. 3c) is marked by an abrupt grain
232 size decrease associated with the shear drag of the oblique Sp foliation in parallelism with C planes
233 (Fig. 3e). Dragged quartz and biotite ribbons are marked by a grain size reduction from 500 μm -1
234 mm to few tens of micrometres in correspondence of the transition zone (Fig. 3e).

235 C planes display a very fine-grained mylonitic foliation characterized by interlayered thin, stretched
236 quartz ribbons and very fine-grained (<10 μm) lepidoblastic sericite-biotite-chlorite aggregates.
237 Quartz ribbons consists of very tiny (<20 μm) equigranular grains with slightly interlobate
238 boundaries and undulose extinction. Ellipsoidal aggregates of sericite, sized 100-200 μm and
239 wrapped by the C foliation, represent pseudomorphs over relic andalusite and cordierite grains. The
240 mylonitic foliation is dragged with top to the east sense of shear along micrometric C' shear bands,
241 with a spacing of some hundreds of microns, marked by very fine-grained phyllosilicates.

242 In quartz-rich layers, the Sp foliation is defined by interlobate aggregates of coarse old grains (100-
243 500 μm) and finer (~50 μm) new grains, both showing a strong preferred orientation (Fig. 3f). New
244 grains are characterized by less elongate elliptical shape and occur associated with subgrains and
245 small bulges of similar size and shape. C shear bands are filled with mixtures of very fine grained
246 chlorite and sericite that abruptly interrupts the S foliation (Fig. 3f).

247

248 **5. Praticciolo: medium to low-temperature ductile-brittle fabric**

249 *5.1. Mesostructures*

250 The Praticciolo cape, located at the southwestern tip of the Calamita peninsula, (Fig. 1) exposes
251 medium metamorphic grade rocks of the Calamita Schists and Calanchiole marble (Fig. 4a). This
252 latter discordantly overlies the Calamita Schists over a low-angle east-dipping fault zone (Figs. 4a,
253 b; Papeschi et al., 2017). The Calamita Schists consists of white mica + biotite + andalusite +
254 cordierite ± chlorite bearing schists and quartzites, while the Calanchiole marble is mostly made of
255 impure and dolomitic marbles with diopside-tremolite-talc-phlogopite paragenesis interlayered with
256 tremolite-talc phyllites.

257 The main foliation (S_p) in the Calamita Schists strikes N-S and dips towards the west at $\sim 30-40^\circ$
258 (Fig. 5a). Mineral lineations, outlined by quartz and biotite aggregates and cordierite and andalusite
259 coarse grains trend east-west and plunge to the west (Fig. 5a). The Calamita Schists are
260 characterized by a strain gradient from weakly foliated schist (low-strain domain) in the northeast to
261 well foliated schists (high-strain domain) in the southwest (Fig. 4b). At outcrop scale, the high
262 strain domain is characterized by decimetre- to metre-thick bands of $S-C'$ with a west/southwest
263 dipping mylonitic foliation (S_m ; Fig. 5a) defined by alternations of stretched quartzite layers and
264 mylonitic biotite-andalusite-bearing schists (Fig. 5c). The mylonitic foliation is displaced by gently
265 east- to west-dipping millimetre-thick C' shear bands that are characterized by top to the east sense
266 of shear (Fig. 5a). They show variable spacing, ranging from few millimetres in mylonitic schists,
267 up to centimetres/decimetres in thick quartzite layers (Fig. 5c). Quartzite layers display shear band
268 boudinage and are offset along C' shear bands with displacements of few millimetres up to some
269 centimetres (Fig. 5c). A second set of steep, C' antithetic west-verging shear bands is sometimes
270 present in thick and coarse quartzite layers wrapped by the S_m , where it intersect synthetic east-
271 verging C' shear bands at closely orthogonal angle (Fig. 5d).

272 The mylonitic fabric is cross-cut by a network of shear fractures and low-angle east dipping faults
273 ($0-15^\circ$; Fig. 5b). Faults are characterized by decimetric to metric eastward displacements and
274 feature a banded cataclastic core zone made up of centimetre-thick unfoliated cataclasite and
275 millimetre-thick foliated ultracataclasite (see below, Fig. 7a). Slickenlines are defined by quartz

276 fibres trending about east-west (Fig. 5b). Shear fractures define a pattern of Riedel shears that,
277 following Logan et al. (1992), correspond to east-verging (i) gently east dipping (0-15°) Y shear
278 fractures, (ii) moderately east dipping (10-30°) synthetic R1 shear fractures and antithetic west-
279 verging (iii) steep (40-70°) R2 shear fractures (Fig. 5b). Displacements range from 1-2 millimetres
280 to some centimetres. This Riedel shear geometry is overall consistent with eastward directed sense
281 of shear. At outcrop scale, a parallelism exists between discrete C' shear bands (Fig. 5c) and Y
282 shear fractures (Fig. 5e). Y shear fractures are often localized on C' shear bands separating boudins
283 of quartz-rich layers (Fig. 5e). R1 shear fractures form en-echelon arrays that connect Y shear
284 fracture segments in step over areas, allowing the linkage between parallel Y shears segments (Fig.
285 5f). Intense damage zones, with a thickness of few centimetres up to decimetres, appear to be
286 characterized by multiple Y, R1 and R2 shear fracture segments that dissect angular blocks of
287 Calamita Schists. In damage zones, Riedel shears - in particular R2 shear fractures - locally exhibit
288 decimetric displacements sometimes cross cutting low-angle fault zones (e.g. Fig. 11a in Papeschi
289 et al., 2017).

290

291 5.2. Microstructures

292 The mylonitic foliation (Sm) is defined by interlayered lepidoblastic mica domains (Fig. 6a) and
293 quartz ribbons (Fig. 6b). Mica domains feature fine-grained (<50 µm) white micas characterized by
294 a strong shape preferred orientation, that are locally dragged along east-verging C' shear bands (Fig.
295 6a). Micas wrap andalusite and cordierite porphyroclasts (200 - 500 µm) and diablastic aggregates
296 of coarse-grained biotite, andalusite and cordierite elongated parallel to the mylonitic foliation. In
297 many cases, andalusite and cordierite grains are substituted by fine-grained aggregates of chlorite
298 and sericite elongated parallel to the Sm (Fig. 6b). Biotite is commonly pseudomorphosed by
299 chlorite.

300 Quartz is characterized by a strongly heterogeneous microfabric. Large, coarse-grained (>500 µm)
301 old quartz grains constitute the cores of large ribbons and boudins (Fig. 6b). They are wrapped by

302 finely recrystallized (~10-100 μm) new quartz grains, produced by subgrain rotation and bulging
303 recrystallization (Fig. 6b) (Papeschi et al., 2017). New grains of uniform grain size are arranged in
304 ribbons stretched parallel to the S_m (Fig. 6b). They show amoeboid to interlobate boundaries and a
305 moderate shape preferred orientation parallel to the S_m . Large areas of ribbons appear extinct at the
306 same time, indicating the presence of a CPO (Fig. 6b). Old quartz grains, which occupy the core of
307 quartz ribbons, are characterized by linear to interlobate grain boundaries with small, localized
308 bulges and recrystallized tiny, new quartz grains (Fig. 6b, d). Grains showing amoeboid boundaries,
309 island grains and reticulate microstructures are locally present as relics largely overprinted by new
310 grains nucleated by subgrain rotation recrystallization. Patchy to undulose extinction patterns (Figs.
311 6d, e) with fine and wide extinction bands (*sensu* Derez et al., 2015) are common within coarse
312 quartz grains.

313 Networks of synthetic (Fig. 6d) and antithetic (Fig. 6e) C' shear bands pass through old quartz
314 grains forming discrete, brittle shear fractures, decorated by trails of very fine-grained (~10 μm)
315 quartz grains and phyllosilicates (sericite and chlorite) with a preferred orientation parallel to the
316 shear bands (Fig. 6c). Synthetic C' shear bands show eastward sense of shear, making a moderate
317 ~20-30° angle in respect to the S_m (Fig. 6d). The antithetic set of C' shear bands shows westward
318 sense of shear and is locally present in thick quartz ribbons where it forms a set of shear fractures
319 conjugate with synthetic shear bands that are closely orthogonal (Fig. 6e). Irregular patterns of
320 fractures with very limited or null slip are associated with conjugate sets of shear bands (Fig. 6e),
321 localized in coarse quartz and quickly dying out when they enter fine-grained quartz ribbons or
322 mica-rich domains.

323 Low-angle faults, occurring parallel to C' shear bands (Fig. 7a), are characterized by a layered
324 microfabric with a foliated ultracataclasite band localized at the contact with the hanging wall block
325 and an unfoliated cataclasite band lying below, closer to the footwall block (Fig. 7b). In the wall
326 rocks, mylonitic deformation features are overprinted by low-grade recrystallization
327 microstructures. Coarse-grained interlobate and amoeboid quartz grains, deformed by grain

328 boundary migration recrystallization, are mantled by aggregates of very fine-grained ($< 20 \mu\text{m}$)
329 quartz grains (Fig. 7c). Trails of very fine-grained quartz define conjugate bands that cross cut
330 coarse quartz grains (Fig. 7c). Shear fractures, filled by a very fine-grained mixture of
331 phyllosilicates, occur inclined to the main fault plane (Fig. 7c). The contact between the wall rock
332 and the ultracataclasite is marked by a millimetre-thick mass of very finely recrystallized ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$)
333 quartz which contains sparse, relic, old quartz grains (Fig. 7d). These latter display conjugate sets
334 of very fine-grained quartz trails, whose shape preferred orientation is oblique to the fault wall (Fig.
335 7d). Sharp shear fractures locally penetrate from the ultracataclasite into the wall rock enveloping
336 recrystallized angular fragments of quartzite. The main foliation (Cf) in the ultracataclasite is
337 outlined by trails of angular wall rock fragments and by coloured bands of sericite and brownish
338 phyllosilicate which represent the cataclasite matrix (Fig. 7e). The cataclastic foliation disappears in
339 the underlying cataclastic band, where the microfabric is characterized by heterometric angular
340 fragments of quartz with microstructures similar to the wall rocks, wrapped by an unfoliated,
341 brownish phyllosilicate-rich matrix.

342

343 **6. Shear band analysis in the Calamita Unit**

344 The attitudes of Sp/Sm foliations and C' shear bands have been measured at outcrop scale at Capo
345 Calvo and the Praticciolo. The Fisher (1959) mean vector to the pole of each measured structural
346 element has been calculated using Stereonet 10 (Allmendinger, 2005). Additional details are
347 available in Appendix A.

348 The angular relationships between foliations (Sp, Sm) and shear bands (C, C') have been also
349 evaluated at the microscale by measuring their relative orientation and their dihedral angles, on a
350 sample from Capo Calvo and 4 samples from the Praticciolo (summary in Tab. 1 and additional
351 details in Appendix A). In the sample from Capo Calvo, the relative orientations of the S, C and C'
352 foliations have been evaluated using the analyze particles routine of the software ImageJ (Schneider
353 et al., 2012) and plotted in rose diagrams using the software OpenStereo (Grohmann and Campania,

354 2010), where the reference line (E-W diameter) corresponds to the average orientation of C shear
355 bands in the field. The S/C and C/C' dihedral angles at Capo Calvo and the Sm/C' dihedral angles
356 at the Praticciolo have been measured directly with the angle tool of the ImageJ software.

357

358 *6.1 Results of shear bands measurements*

359 At Capo Calvo the mean pole to the Sp foliation is $240.9/57.2 \pm 12.0^\circ$ (1σ) and the average pole to
360 C' shear bands is $242.5/37.1 \pm 12.8^\circ$ (Tab. 1). The average Sp/C' acute dihedral angle is 37.1 ± 8.7 .
361 Thin section scale measurements on the Capo Calvo sample (Fig. 8a) provide an average Sp/C'
362 dihedral angle of $41.9 \pm 4.6^\circ$, an Sp/C dihedral angle of $21.1 \pm 4.6^\circ$ and a C/C' dihedral angle of
363 $15.2 \pm 1.9^\circ$ (Tab. 1). At the Praticciolo cape, the mesoscale Sm foliation has a mean pole of
364 $79.2/56.9 \pm 15.1^\circ$ while the average pole to C' shear bands is oriented at $70.5/87.1 \pm 9.1^\circ$ (synthetic
365 C') and $47.3/18.2 \pm 39.5^\circ$ (antithetic C'). The average acute dihedral angle between Sm and synthetic
366 C' shears corresponds to $30.2 \pm 8.8^\circ$ and the average obtuse dihedral angle between synthetic and
367 antithetic C' shear bands is $110.9 \pm 20.3^\circ$ (Tab. 1). Similar values of Sm/C' dihedral angles have
368 been obtained from the thin section measurements, ranging between $31.2 \pm 3.1^\circ$ (minimum) and
369 $38.4 \pm 3.7^\circ$ (maximum) (Tab. 1).

370 Figure 8 shows an example of the angular relationships between foliation and shear bands from the
371 Capo Calvo sample. The sample displays the contact between high grade schists with Sp foliation
372 and a mylonitic centimetre-thick C shear band (Fig. 8a). C shear bands define a strong maximum
373 with 52% of the C planes measurements oriented close to the sample horizontal, while Sp foliation
374 planes appear more scattered (Fig. 8b). Based on microstructural observations, we observed a
375 progressive decrease of the Sp/C dihedral angle within the lozenge approaching the contact with the
376 C shear band (Fig. 8a). Therefore we distinguished three subdomains: (i) the wall rock, (ii) the Sp/C
377 contact, corresponding to the area within 1 centimetre from the contact with the C shear band (Fig.
378 8a) and (iii) the C shear band itself, where the Sp foliation is not present. Within the wall rock
379 subdomain the mean Sp/C dihedral angle is $36.7 \pm 2.4^\circ$ (Fig. 8c) whereas in the Sp/C contact

380 subdomain the mean Sp/C dihedral angle is reduced to just $21.1 \pm 3.4^\circ$ and Sp and C orientations
381 locally overlaps (Fig. 8d). This highlights the progressive decrease of the Sp/C dihedral angle
382 approaching the C shear band subdomain. In the latter, the Sp is not present and C' shear bands,
383 oriented at $\sim 15^\circ$ in respect to C shear bands (Fig. 8e) occur.

384

385 **7. Discussion**

386 *7.1. Shear zones in the Calamita Unit: geometry and evolution*

387 The studied sections in the Calamita Unit represent an example in which deformation evolves in a
388 very short time span (~ 800 Ky; Musumeci et al., 2015) from metre to decametre-thick ductile high-
389 strain domains to narrow and localized brittle shear zones (Papeschi et al., 2017). Deformation
390 occurred during cooling of metamorphic rocks at low pressure conditions (< 0.18 - 0.20 GPa).
391 Assuming (i) an uplift/erosion rate between 1 and 2 mm/yr and (ii) an average density of 2.7 g/cm^3
392 a vertical exhumation of 800 - 1600 metres, (0.02-0.04 GPa) can be estimated and therefore
393 pressure can be considered nearly constant during deformation.

394 The earlier fabric, represented by a high grade metamorphic foliation, has been overprinted by shear
395 bands (Fig. 9a). At peak metamorphic conditions (600 - 650°C), fast grain boundary migration,
396 recorded within coarse grained quartz ribbons, allows deformation to be distributed within high
397 strain domains. Grain boundary migration was likely promoted by fluid circulation, which in the
398 examined high metamorphic grade metapelites can derive from (i) dehydration metamorphic
399 reactions (i.e. muscovite-out reaction; Pattison and Tracy, 1992) and (ii) hydrothermal fluids
400 originated from the host igneous rocks (Porto Azzurro pluton and felsic dykes; Dini et al., 2008).

401 The transition to C shear bands (Fig. 9a) is marked by (i) a sharp decrease in grain size (Fig. 3c, e,
402 f) and (ii) the widespread growth of sericite-chlorite bearing metamorphic assemblages (Fig. 3c, e).

403 These latter occurs as retrograde alteration of previous mineral assemblage (i.e. andalusite,
404 cordierite and K-feldspar) and indicates low temperature conditions ($T < 400$ - 450°C) and circulation
405 of intragranular water-rich fluids.

406 High-temperature quartz microstructures are overprinted by new quartz grains resulting from low-
407 to medium- temperature bulging and subgrain rotation recrystallization (Stipp et al., 2002), as
408 already suggested by Papeschi et al. (2017). Evidence of subgrain rotation recrystallization is
409 highlighted by the oblique orientation of new quartz grains with respect to C shear bands orientation
410 (Fig. 3f), recrystallizing along the extensional instantaneous stretching axis of the flow (Law et al.,
411 1984; Wallis, 1995). In the most deformed domains C shear bands evolve to mylonitic shear zones
412 with a continuous mylonitic foliation (Fig. 9b), characterized by fine-grained quartz ribbons and
413 mixed quartz-sericite layers (e.g. Fig. 3e). Strain hardening of the quartzo-feldspathic domains (i.e.
414 relic high grade foliation) outside and/or enveloped by shear bands (Fig. 9a) favoured strain
415 localization during temperature decrease into C shear bands, via reaction softening with fluid influx
416 and growth of soft phyllosilicates (e.g. Stunitz and Tullis, 2001; Jessel et al., 2009; Bukovská et al.,
417 2016), enhancing grain size sensitive creep (Kilian et al., 2011; Viegas et al., 2016). The decrease of
418 the Sp/C dihedral angles and the parallelism between the two foliations at the shear zone boundary
419 (Fig. 8c, d) indicate a passive rotation of the Sp foliation towards the orientation of C shear bands.
420 A similar evolution has been documented by Berthé et al. (1979) in the South Armorican Shear
421 Zone, where they observed decrease of dihedral angles with increasing strain and the reactivation of
422 the S foliation as C shear planes. Therefore, the evolution from localized shear bands (Fig. 9a) to
423 wider shear zones with a well developed mylonitic foliation (Fig. 9c) has been accomplished by (i)
424 passive rotation and deformation of the high grade Sp foliation and (ii) linkage of anastomosing
425 shear zones that coalesced and consumed low-strain domains, similarly to the Cap de Creus
426 example described by Fusseis et al. (2006).

427 The mylonitic foliation is overprinted by discontinuous C' shear bands (Fig. 9c). In phyllosilicate-
428 rich domains C' shear bands are characterized by the shear drag of mica and chlorite grains (Fig.
429 6a), suggesting that they formed by re-orientating pre-existing phyllosilicates parallel to the shear
430 band itself (e.g. Jessel et al., 2009). On the other hand, in competent layers (i.e. thick and coarse-
431 grained quartz ribbons) C' shear bands form oppositely verging conjugate sets (Fig. 6e) marked by

432 fine-grained phyllosilicates indicative of low temperature conditions ($T < 400$ °C). The incipient
433 stage of C' shear band development is marked by trails of very fine-grained (~ 10 μm) new quartz
434 grains (Fig. 6e), which might indicate low temperature bulging recrystallization. The development
435 of conjugate shear bands in coarse quartz grains (Fig. 6e) might be related to the increasing effect of
436 competency contrast at low temperature conditions (greenschist facies), driving strain hardening of
437 'coarse and stiff' quartz grains (e.g. Menegon et al., 2008). Patterns of fractures, associated with C'
438 shear bands, indicate that they formed by brittle mechanisms. Thus coarse quartz grains experienced
439 a progressive embrittlement while the surrounding fine grained mylonitic foliation (quartz new
440 grains and phyllosilicates) was still deforming in a ductile way. The growth of phyllosilicates and
441 fine-grained quartz on C' shear bands could have been produced by low temperature
442 recrystallization and/or precipitation from a fluid phase, as shown by Kjøl et al. (2015).

443 These features, from a natural example, are consistent with the nucleation of C' shear bands as a
444 consequence of rheological heterogeneities as shown by the experimental data of Holyoke and
445 Tullis (2006) and the numerical model of Jessel et al. (2009).

446

447 *7.2. Brittle-ductile transition: shear fractures and role of precursory shear bands.*

448 The entirely-brittle stage of shear zone activity is evidenced by Y shear fractures parallel to C' shear
449 bands (Fig. 9d) and subsidiary shear fractures that outline a network of R1 and R2 Riedel shears
450 consistent with top to the east sense of shear parallel to the ductile direction of tectonic transport
451 (Fig. 5a, b). Moreover some fault zones, parallel to Y shear fractures (Fig. 5b), preserve in their
452 wall rocks trails and aggregates of very fine quartz grains (Fig. 7c, d). These microstructures are
453 cross cut by brittle shear fractures and are preserved in angular quartz-rich clasts embedded in the
454 cataclasite (Fig. 9b), indicating that low temperature recrystallization occurred before brittle failure.
455 These features may be consistent with nucleation of faults and shear fractures close to the brittle-
456 ductile transition with low temperature recrystallization overprinted by brittle deformation.

457 The strict relationships between C' shear bands and Y shear fractures, highlighted by their
458 parallelism (Fig. 5a, b) and the observed localization of Y shears in correspondence of C' shear
459 bands (Fig. 5e), suggest that C' shear bands acted as precursors for Y shear fractures. At the
460 microscale, C' shear bands in competent domains bear evidence of recrystallization associated to
461 brittle fracturing (e.g. Fig. 6e). This latter can be considered the incipient stage of fracture
462 propagation at the brittle-ductile transition. The brittle reactivation of C' shear bands could be
463 favoured by the presence of low-friction coefficient phyllosilicates (Zhang and He, 2016).
464 Differently, the main mylonitic foliation (Sm), although characterized by fine-grained sericite layers
465 (e.g. Fig. 6b), does not show any evidence of brittle reactivation. This feature could be related to the
466 different orientation of shear bands and the Sm with respect to the maximum stress (σ_1) in the
467 brittle regime. R1 and R2 shears are active simultaneously with Y shears (Logan et al., 1992),
468 therefore the paleo-orientation of σ_1 (i.e. the bisector plane of the mean conjugate R1 and R2
469 shears; Fig. 10a) can be estimated. The calculated mean σ_1 direction is oriented $97.3/38.2 \pm 19.1^\circ$
470 and σ_3 at $267.3/51.8 \pm 19.1^\circ$. The σ_1 orientation lies makes a $\sim 30\text{-}40^\circ$ angle with the average
471 orientation of C' shear bands (dip/dipdir: 03/250) and is roughly orthogonal to the Sm foliation
472 (33/261) (Fig. 10a). Slip tendency analyses have been performed using the program FaultKin
473 (Allmendinger et al., 1992), assuming zero pore fluid pressure and the same coefficient of static
474 friction μ for the Sm foliation and shear bands. Several values of μ , between 0.2 and 0.7, have been
475 used at varying conditions of differential stress (10-150 Mpa) to evaluate the slip tendency Ts
476 (Morris et al., 1996). In Fig. 10b the slip tendency analysis for C' shear bands and the Sm foliations
477 is shown for a μ value of 0.45 and a differential stress of 80 MPa. Under these conditions, C' shear
478 bands display the highest probability to reactivate (red circles in Fig. 10b) whereas the Sm foliation
479 show low slip tendency (cyan circles in Fig. 10b). These values fit well with the observed natural
480 structures. Slip on the Sm foliation can be promoted by increasing the differential stress and/or the
481 pore fluid pressure or by decreasing the μ coefficient. Thus, differential stress and the coefficient of
482 static friction exert a strong control over the reactivation of ductile precursors and hence over the

483 geometries of brittle structures. The favourable orientation for brittle reactivation of C' shear bands
484 can be visualized by plotting the average orientation of C' shear bands and the S_m on the Mohr
485 circle (Fig. 10c). In this example two cohesion-less failure envelopes have been plotted, one for
486 general failure ($\mu=0.7$) and the other for failure along shear bands/foliation ($\mu=0.45$). Although in
487 this example both C' shear bands and the S_m are equally weak ($\mu=0.45$), the S_m is so unfavourably
488 oriented in respect to σ_1 that failure takes place across the foliation (R1 shears) (Fig. 10c).

489 This situation is similar to the experiments on sheared foliated rocks performed by Ikari et al.
490 (2015) on a foliated black slate at various orientations in respect to the applied shear stress. In the
491 experimental setting with foliation dipping in the opposite direction in respect to the shear sense
492 (Fig. 10d), these authors observed the early nucleation of R1 shears across the foliation. Failure
493 along the foliation occurs only at higher shear stresses with the formation of foliation-parallel P
494 shears (Fig. 10d). These authors concluded that under these conditions the main foliation is
495 unfavourably oriented for slip and therefore R1 shears are forced to form from early stages of
496 deformation (see also Sibson, 1985; Collettini and Sibson, 2001).

497 We suggest that the high strain domain in the Calamita Schists represent a natural analogue of the
498 experiment of Ikari et al. (2015). In respect to the experiments of Ikari et al. (2015), the presence of
499 a second set of weakness planes, represented by C' shear bands, might have caused the early
500 localization of deformation onto precursory C' shear bands, producing networks of Y and R1
501 shears. This might have also inhibited the reactivation of the foliation λ , which has been observed by
502 Ikari et al. (2015). Therefore we propose that at the brittle-ductile transition deformation switched
503 progressively from the well developed mylonitic foliation into discordant networks of shear
504 fractures that formed as a consequence of the reactivation of precursory shear bands in the brittle
505 regime.

506

507 *7.3 Shear zone flow and shear band orientation.*

508 The orientation of C' shear bands within a shear zone is thought to be related to the degree of non-
509 coaxiality of the shear zone (Law et al., 2004) and can be used to estimate the vorticity of the flow
510 (Kurz and Northrup, 2008).

511 At the Praticciolo, the mean dihedral angle between the Sm and C' shear bands measured at the
512 mesoscale ($30.2 \pm 8.8^\circ$) overlaps with the $\sim 30\text{-}38^\circ$ values (Tab. 1) calculated at thin section scale.
513 This suggests that C' shear bands lie on average at a constant orientation and they have not
514 significantly rotated after their formation. According to the model of Grasemann et al. (2003), a
515 stable orientation of shear bands is predicted for orientations of $\sim 30^\circ$ to the foliation in general
516 shear. According to Simpson and De Paor (1993) and Kurz and Northrup (2008), the dihedral angle
517 between synthetic C' shear bands and the foliation corresponds to half the acute angle (v in Eq. 1)
518 between the flow apophyses, which is related to the vorticity number W_k by the equation:

$$519 \cos(v) = W_k \quad (1)$$

520 Based on the assumption that C' shear bands lie in a stable orientation, from Eq. 1 a W_k of $\sim 0.3 -$
521 0.5 can be estimated for the Praticciolo section (Fig. 10e). The fluctuation between the calculated
522 values (see Appendix A) is related to the uncertainties of the method rather than to vorticity changes
523 in the shear zone (see discussion in Xypolias, 2010). As shown in Fig. 10e, antithetic C' shear
524 bands plot at lower angles in respect to the obtuse bisector of the flow and this could indicate that
525 they have experienced a forward rotation. This fits well with the model of Grasemann et al. (2003),
526 which suggests that shear bands at high angle ($>90^\circ$) are expected to rotate rapidly towards the
527 fabric attractor of the flow. The recognized stable orientation of synthetic shear bands and rotation
528 of antithetic surfaces might be interpreted as a result of C' shear band development in a stable
529 orientation with the general zone flow during the late stage of deformation as documented by
530 Gillam et al. (2014) in the Alpine Fault.

531

532 **8. Conclusions.**

533 We document an example of high strain domains where deformation evolved from high to low
534 temperature conditions. An earlier high grade foliation was overprinted by several generations of
535 shear bands marked by the retrograde growth of phyllosilicates and ductile to brittle deformation.
536 Strain localization appears to have been mainly controlled by temperature decrease and coeval fluid
537 circulation that favoured reaction softening and grain size reduction. Close to the brittle-ductile
538 transition the effect of competency contrast favoured strain concentration within weak layers
539 leaving behind fractured ‘stiff’ domains. The transition from ductile to brittle deformation occurred
540 during continuous shearing, rather than due to a later brittle reactivation, leading to the extreme
541 localization of deformation from decimetric to metric ductile shear zones into a network of discrete
542 faults and shear fractures.

543

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548

549 **Appendix A. Supplementary Material**

550 Supplementary material for this article is available online.

551

552 **Figure captions**

553 **Fig. 1** – Simplified geological map of southeastern Elba Island (modified after Papeschi et al.,
554 2017). Squares highlight the location of the two studied sections. CNT: Capo Norsì thrust. CSZ:
555 Calanchiole shear zone. FSZ: Felciaio shear zone. ZF: Zuccale fault. Mineral abbreviations: Ab:
556 albite; And: andalusite; Bt: biotite; Crd: cordierite; Di: diopside; Wmca: white mica; Kfs: K-
557 feldspar; Phl: phlogopite; Tr: tremolite; Wo: wollastonite.

558

559 **Fig. 2** – **(a)** Simplified geological map of Capo Calvo with sample and figure location. The
560 stereographic projection (equal angle, lower hemisphere) shows poles to the main foliation (Sp), C'
561 shear bands and the mineral lineation (Lp). The ellipse marks the trace of the 95% confidence cone
562 of the mean lineation vector (yellow star). Sample details are available in Appendix A. **(b-c)**
563 Mesoscale features of Capo Calvo: **(b)** Shear band cleavage characterized by moderately east
564 dipping C shear bands (violet arrow) that cross cut the main metamorphic foliation (Sp). Lozenges
565 of weakly foliated andalusite-cordierite-biotite aggregates (yellow arrow) occur wrapped by the Sp.
566 A single C' shear band (red arrow) is also visible. **(c)** Mylonitic shear zone characterized by
567 stretched andalusite-cordierite-biotite pods (red arrow) parallel to the mylonitic foliation (Sm). Note
568 the steeply east dipping C' shear bands that cross cut the Sm.

569
570
571 **Fig. 3** –Microstructures of Capo Calvo taken under crossed polarizers. **(a)** Microfabric of the Sp
572 continuous schistosity (yellow dotted line), marked by alternations of coarse grained quartz with
573 amoeboid grain boundaries and scattered parallel biotite grains. Pinning microstructures are also
574 present. **(b)** Detail of a coarse K-feldspar porphyroblast wrapped by the Sp foliation (yellow dotted
575 line). The K-feldspar porphyroblast is characterized by pecilitic inclusions of biotite and coronas of
576 sericite-biotite. **(c)** Thin section image stitching showing the contact between the oblique Sp
577 foliation (below) and the C mylonitic foliation (above). Note the difference in grain size between
578 the coarse-grained Sp foliation and fine-grained C shear band. Squares mark locations of Figs. 3d,
579 e. **(d)** Detail of the oblique Sp foliation marked by alternations of biotite layers and coarse quartz
580 ribbons with core and mantle structure. **(e)** Contact between the Sp (lower right corner) and the C
581 shear band (top left corner) marked by the sharp decrease in grain size to fine-grained quartz,
582 chlorite and sericite in the C shear band and the sinistral shear drag of the Sp foliation (purple
583 arrow). **(f)** Microfabric of a quartz-rich lozenge wrapped in a C shear band. Note the oblique Sp
584 foliation marked by the preferred orientation of both old and new, recrystallized quartz grains.

585 Mineral abbreviations: And: andalusite; Bt: biotite; Crd: cordierite; Kfs: K-feldspar; Qtz: quartz;
586 Ser: sericite.

587

588 **Fig. 4** – Mesoscale features of the Praticciolo area. **(a)** Simplified geological map of the Praticciolo
589 cape with indicated location of samples and figures. Sample details are available in Appendix A. **(b)**
590 **(above)** Photo panorama along the section marked in Fig. 4a. The southwestern side of the area is
591 characterized by a high strain domain with mylonites, whereas in the northeastern side the dominant
592 fabric is represented by low strain schists. Samples projected on the section are marked by green
593 dots. **(below)** Interpreted photo panorama with lithologies coloured as in Fig. 4a.

594

595 **Fig. 5** – Mesoscale structures of the Calamita Schists at the Praticciolo. **(a)** Stereographic projection
596 (equal angle, lower hemisphere) showing poles to C' shear bands, the main foliation and mineral
597 lineations. The ellipse marks the trace of the 95% confidence cone of the mean lineation vector
598 (yellow star). **(b)** Stereographic projection (equal angle, lower hemisphere) showing poles to low-
599 angle brittle faults, Riedel Y, R1 and R2 shear fractures and brittle slickenlines. **(c)** Mylonitic fabric
600 characterized by west dipping mylonitic foliation (Sm) with parallel quartzitic and foliated schistose
601 bands. Asymmetric boudinage of quartzite layers occurs along C' shear bands. **(d)** Conjugate
602 synthetic (C'1) and antithetic (C'2) C' shear bands developed in a quartz-rich lens wrapped by the
603 Sm foliation. The inserted stereographic projection (equal angle, lower hemisphere) shows the
604 orientation of antithetic (in red) and synthetic (in blue) C' shear bands. **(e)** Mylonitic schists with
605 top to the east C' shear bands overprinted by top to the east Y shear fractures (red arrow). **(f)**
606 Network of east-verging subhorizontal Y shear fractures bridged by moderately dipping R1 shear
607 fractures that overprint the main west dipping metamorphic foliation.

608

609 **Fig. 6** – Microphotographs of the Praticciolo section taken under crossed polarisers. **(a)**
610 Alternations of lepidoblastic mica-rich domains and quartz ribbons elongated parallel to the Sm

611 (yellow dotted line) that wraps sheared pinitized cordierite porphyroclasts. East-verging C' shear
612 bands (red dotted line) are also visible. **(b)** Mylonitic foliation (Sm) characterized by thick
613 alternations of coarse and fine-grained quartz ribbons and sericite layers. Nodules of sericite-
614 chlorite represent pseudomorphs over andalusite-cordierite porphyroclasts. Note coarse quartz
615 grains (upper left corner) mantled by finely recrystallized grains. The insert shows a detail of quartz
616 ribbons with gypsum plate inserted highlighting the quartz CPO. **(c)** Conjugate synthetic (red
617 arrow) and antithetic (purple arrow) C' shear fractures localized within quartz and associated with
618 coarse chlorite grains. Note the finely recrystallized quartz and chlorite in their cores. **(d)** Synthetic
619 dextral C' shear fractures (red arrow) localized in a coarse-grained quartz ribbon at a gentle angle in
620 respect to the mylonitic foliation (Sm). **(e)** Detail of a very coarse (500-900 μm) quartz ribbon
621 mantled by recrystallized quartz grains and chlorite-sericite aggregates defining the Sm. Note the
622 conjugate C' shear fractures associated with fracturing within coarse grains (sketched in the lower
623 right corner) and the patchy undulose extinction of quartz. Mineral abbreviations: And: andalusite;
624 Chl: chlorite; Crd: cordierite; Qtz: quartz; Ser: sericite; Wmca: white mica.

625
626 **Fig. 7** – Microfabric of low-angle brittle faults. **(a)** Mesoscale features of the core zone of a low-
627 angle brittle fault. A foliated ultracataclasite band (Sc = cataclastic foliation) occurs on top of
628 unfoliated cataclasites. Note the discordant contact with both footwall and hanging wall foliation
629 (Sp). The red rectangle highlights the sampling site of the thin section of Fig. 7b. **(b-c-d)**
630 Microphotographs collected under crossed polarizers. **(b)** Photo stitching of the entire thin section
631 of Fig. 7a, showing a band of unfoliated cataclasite (bottom) band of foliated ultracataclasite
632 (middle) and the contact with the quartzite in the hanging wall (top). **(c)** Detail of the wall rock
633 microfabric: coarse quartz grains with amoeboid grain boundaries are mantled by small bulges of
634 tiny new grains. Red dotted lines highlight trails of recrystallized quartz grains. The yellow arrow
635 marks a sericite-filled shear fracture. **(d)** Detail of the contact zone (cyan arrow) between the wall
636 rock (above) and the cataclasite (below). The transition corresponds to a domain of very fine-

637 grained quartz containing relic quartz grains with conjugate trails of recrystallized grains (purple
638 arrow). (e) Microphotograph at parallel polarizers of the ultracataclasite band showing a cataclastic
639 foliation (Sc) defined by parallel trails of angular fragments and a banded matrix with brownish
640 phyllosilicates

641

642 **Fig. 8** – Example of the analysis of dihedral angles between the Sp foliation (lower half of Fig. 9a)
643 and C-C' shear band planes (upper half of Fig. 9a) at the Capo Calvo section (sample SP196; details
644 in Appendix A). (a) Photo stitching of thin section SP196 under crossed polarisers. Three
645 subdomains can be distinguished on a microstructural basis; the Sp domain (bottom), the Sp/C
646 contact (centre) and the C shear band (top). (b-c-d-e) Rose diagrams illustrating the distribution of
647 the Sp foliation and C-C' shear band planes. Radius lines are every 22.5° and the histogram interval
648 is set at 5°. Inner circle interval is set at 5% of total number of measurements. The cumulative
649 maxima and the calculated dihedral angles are shown. See text for further details. (b) Sp and C
650 orientations collected in the entire sample. (c) Sp and C orientations collected within the wall rock
651 subdomain. (d) Sp and C orientations collected at the Sp/C contact subdomain. (e) C and C'
652 orientations from the C shear band subdomain.

653

654 **Fig. 9** – Sketch illustrating the evolution of mylonites in high-strain domains from peak
655 metamorphic conditions (~650 °C) to the brittle regime (< ~300 °C). Coin for scale. (a) Network of
656 white mica-bearing top to the east C shear bands that wrap lozenges bearing the high-grade Sp
657 foliation. (b) Mylonite with a continuous Sm foliation consisting of mica-rich bands and stretched
658 andalusite-cordierite-biotite pods, associated with top to the east C' shear bands. (c) White mica
659 bearing mylonite with strong Sm foliation wrapping quartz-rich layers displaced by synthetic top to
660 the east C' shear bands. (d) White mica bearing mylonite with quartzite boudins segmented along
661 top to the east C' shear bands. C' shear bands have been reactivated along Y shear fractures with
662 synthetic top to the east sense of shear. See text for discussion. (*): peak temperature for the

663 Calamita Schists by Duranti et al., 1992. (**): temperature of chlorite bearing assemblage by
664 Pattison and Tracy (1992). (***) : brittle/ductile transition in quartz after Voll (1976).

665

666 **Fig. 10** – (a) Block diagram illustrating the calculated mean orientation (expressed in dip/dip
667 direction) of ductile and brittle structural elements and the calculated direction of the σ_1 . (b)
668 Example of slip tendency analysis of the Sm foliation and C' shear bands for $\mu=0.45$ and $\Delta\sigma=80$
669 MPa. Foliations are coloured in respect to the slip tendency Ts (Morris et al., 1996). See text for
670 comment. (c) Sketched Mohr-Coulomb diagram with plotted failure envelopes for $\mu=0.7$ and
671 $\mu=0.45$. The average orientation of C' shear bands, the Sm foliation and R1 shears in respect to σ_1
672 is shown in the Mohr circle. The shaded area represents orientations of pre-existing foliations that
673 are likely to be reactivated before failure across foliation takes place. See text for details. (d) Failure
674 experiment performed by Ikari et al. (2015) for a sample of Pennsylvania slate with foliation
675 dipping in the opposite direction to the applied shearing. At low shear strain failure across foliation
676 takes place with the nucleation of R1 shears. Then, at higher shear strain, the main foliation is
677 reactivated by P shears. (e) Rose diagram showing the orientations of synthetic and antithetic C'
678 shear bands for the Praticciolo section in respect to the main foliation, which marks the extensional
679 flow apophysis (A_2). The grey shaded area represents the outcrop average. Black bars denote each
680 sample average. Black dashed lines mark the bisectors of the apophyses. The position of the
681 contractional flow apophysis (A_1) is based on the calculations of the vorticity number W_k . See text
682 for further details.

683

684 **Table captions**

685 **Tab. 1** – Calculated mean attitude of structural elements and shear band geometries at the meso-
686 and the microscale. Errors at 1σ .

687

688 **References**

- 689 Allmendinger, R. W., 2005. Stereonet. Program for stereographic projection.
690
- 691 Allmendinger, R. W., Marrett, R. A., Cladouhos, T., 1992. FaultKin. A program for analyzing fault
692 slip data.
693
- 694 Anderson, E.M., 1951. Dynamics of Faulting and Dyke Formations with Application to Britain.
695 Oliver & Boy, Edinburgh.
696
- 697 Austrheim, H., & Boundy, T. M., 1994. Pseudotachylytes generated during seismic faulting and
698 eclogitization of the deep crust. *Science* 265(5168), 82-84.
699
- 700 Barberi, F., Innocenti, F., Ricci, C. A., 1967. Il complesso scistoso di Capo Calamita (Isola d'Elba).
701 *Atti Soc. Toscana Sci. Nat. Pisa, Mem., P.V., Ser. A* 72 (2), 579–617.
702
- 703 Bianco, C., Brogi, A., Caggianelli, A., Giorgetti, G., Liotta, D., Meccheri, M., 2015. HP-LT
704 metamorphism in Elba Island: Implications for the geodynamic evolution of the inner Northern
705 Apennines (Italy). *Journal of Geodynamics* 91, 13-25.
706
- 707 Berthé, D., Choukroune, P., Gapais, D., 1979. Orientations préférentielles du quartz et
708 orthogneissification progressive en régime cisailant: l'exemple du cisaillement sud-
709 armoricain. *Bull. Mineral.* 102, 265-272.
710
- 711 Bistacchi, A., Massironi, M., Menegon, L., Bolognesi, F., Donghi, V., 2012. On the nucleation of
712 non-Andersonian faults along phyllosilicate-rich mylonite belts. Geological Society, London,
713 *Special Publications* 367(1), 185-199.

714

715 Boccaletti, M., Elter, P., Guazzone, G., 1971. Plate tectonic models for the development of the
716 Western Alps and Northern Apennines. *Nature* 234(49), 108-111.

717

718 Bucher, K., Grapes, R., 2011. Metamorphism of pelitic rocks (metapelites). In: *Petrogenesis of*
719 *Metamorphic Rocks* (pp. 257-313). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

720

721 Bukovská, Z., Jeřábek, P., Morales, L. F., 2016. Major softening at brittle-ductile transition due to
722 interplay between chemical and deformation processes: An insight from evolution of shear bands in
723 the South Armorican Shear Zone. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth* 121(2), 1158-1182.

724

725 Butler, R.W.H., Bond, C.E., Shipton, Z.K., Jones, R.R., Casey, M., 2008. Fabric anisotropy controls
726 faulting in the continental crust. *J. Geological Soc. Lond.* 165, 449–452.

727

728 Carreras, J., Czeck, D.M., Druguet, E., Hudleston, P.J., 2010. Structure and development of an
729 anastomosing network of ductile shear zones. *J. Struct. Geol.* 32 (5), 656-666.

730

731 Collettini, C., Sibson, R. H., 2001. Normal faults, normal friction? *Geology* 29(10), 927-930.

732

733 Collettini, C., Holdsworth, R. E., 2004. Fault zone weakening and character of slip along low-angle
734 normal faults: insights from the Zuccale fault, Elba, Italy. *Journal of the Geological Society* 161(6),
735 1039-1051.

736

737 Collettini, C., Niemeijer, A., Viti, C., Marone, C., 2009. Fault zone fabric and fault
738 weakness. *Nature* 462(7275), 907-910.

739

- 740 Cox, S. F., 2010. The application of failure mode diagrams for exploring the roles of fluid pressure
741 and stress states in controlling styles of fracture-controlled permeability enhancement in faults and
742 shear zones. *Geofluids* 10(1-2), 217-233.
- 743
- 744 Debenedetti, A., 1953. Osservazioni geologiche nelle zone minerarie dell'Isola d'Elba. *Bollettino*
745 *del Servizio Geologico d'Italia* 74, 35-70.
- 746
- 747 Derez, T., Pennock, G., Drury, M., Sintubin, M., 2015. Low-temperature intracrystalline
748 deformation microstructures in quartz. *Journal of Structural Geology* 71, 3-23.
- 749
- 750 Dini, A., Mazzarini, F., Musumeci, G., Rocchi, S., 2008. Multiple hydro-fracturing by boron-rich
751 fluids in the Late Miocene contact aureole of eastern Elba Island (Tuscany, Italy). *Terra*
752 *Nova* 20(4), 318-326.
- 753
- 754 Duranti, S., Palmeri, R., Pertusati, P. C., Ricci, C. A., 1992. Geological evolution and metamorphic
755 petrology of the basal sequences of eastern Elba (complex II). *Acta Vulcanologica* 2, 213-229.
- 756
- 757 Ebert, A., Herwegh, M., Pfiffner, A., 2007. Cooling induced strain localization in carbonate
758 mylonites within a large-scale shear zone (Glarus thrust, Switzerland). *J. Struct. Geol.* 29, 1164-
759 1184.
- 760
- 761 Fossen, H., Cavalcante, G. C. G., 2017. Shear zones—A review. *Earth-Science Reviews* 171, 434-
762 455.
- 763
- 764 Fusseis, F., Handy, M. R., Schrank, C., 2006. Networking of shear zones at the brittle-to-viscous
765 transition (Cap de Creus, NE Spain). *Journal of Structural Geology* 28(7), 1228-1243.

766

767 Gapais, D., 1989. Shear structures within deformed granites: mechanical and thermal
768 indicators. *Geology* 17(12), 1144-1147.

769

770 Gerald, J. D. F., Mancktelow, N. S., Pennacchioni, G., Kunze, K., 2006. Ultrafine-grained quartz
771 mylonites from high-grade shear zones: Evidence for strong dry middle to lower crust. *Geology*
772 34(5), 369-372.

773

774 Gillam, B. G., Little, T. A., Smith, E., Toy, V. G., 2014. Reprint of Extensional shear band
775 development on the outer margin of the Alpine mylonite zone, Tatara Stream, Southern Alps, New
776 Zealand. *Journal of Structural Geology* 64, 115-134.

777

778 Gleason, G. C., Tullis, J., 1995. A flow law for dislocation creep of quartz aggregates determined
779 with the molten salt cell. *Tectonophysics* 247(1), 1-23.

780

781 Graham, R. H., 1980. The role of shear belts in the structural evolution of the South Harris igneous
782 complex. *Journal of Structural Geology* 2(1-2), 29-37.

783

784 Grasmann, B., Stüwe, K., Vannay, J. C., 2003. Sense and non-sense of shear in flanking
785 structures. *Journal of Structural Geology* 25(1), 19-34.

786

787 Grohmann, C. H., Campanha, G. A., 2010. OpenStereo: open source, cross-platform software for
788 structural geology analysis. In: AGU Fall Meeting abstracts.

789

790 Hippertt, J., Rocha, A., Lana, C., Egydio-Silva, M., Takeshita, T., 2001. Quartz plastic segregation
791 and ribbon development in high-grade striped gneisses. *Journal of Structural Geology* 23(1), 67-80.

792

793 Hirth, G., Tullis, J., 1992. Dislocation creep regimes in quartz aggregates. *Journal of Structural*
794 *Geology* 14(2), 145-159.

795

796 Hirth, G., Tullis, J., 1994. The brittle-plastic transition in experimentally deformed quartz
797 aggregates. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth* 99(B6), 11731-11747.

798

799 Holyoke, C.W., Tullis, J., 2006. Mechanisms of weak phase interconnection and the effects of
800 phase strength contrast on fabric development. *Journal of Structural Geology* 28, 621-640.

801

802 Ikari, M. J., Niemeijer, A. R., Marone, C., 2015. Experimental investigation of incipient shear
803 failure in foliated rock. *Journal of Structural Geology* 77, 82-91.

804

805 Jackson, J. A., Austrheim, H., McKenzie, D., Priestley, K., 2004. Metastability, mechanical
806 strength, and the support of mountain belts. *Geology* 32, 625-628.

807

808 Jessell, M. W., 1987. Grain-boundary migration microstructures in a naturally deformed
809 quartzite. *Journal of Structural Geology* 9(8), 1007-1014.

810

811 Jessell, M.W., Bons, P.D., Griera, A., Evans, L.A., Wilson, C.J.L., 2009. A tale of two viscosities.
812 *Journal of Structural Geology* 31 (7), 719-736.

813

814 Ji, S., Jiang, Z., Rybacki, E., Wirth, R., Prior, D., Xia, B., 2004. Strain softening and microstructural
815 evolution of anorthite aggregates and quartz-anorthite layered composites deformed in torsion.

816 *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 222, 377-390.

817

818 Keller, J. V. A., Coward, M. P., 1996. The structure and evolution of the Northern Tyrrhenian
819 Sea. *Geological Magazine* 133(1), 1-16.

820

821 Kilian, R., Heilbronner, R., Stünitz, H., 2011. Quartz grain size reduction in a granitoid rock and the
822 transition from dislocation to diffusion creep. *Journal of Structural Geology* 33(8), 1265-1284.

823

824 Kjøl, H. J., Viola, G., Menegon, L., Sørensen, B. E., 2015. Brittle-viscous deformation of vein
825 quartz under fluid-rich lower greenschist facies conditions. *Solid Earth* 6(2), 681.

826

827 Kurz, G. A., Northrup, C. J., 2008. Structural analysis of mylonitic rocks in the Cougar Creek
828 Complex, Oregon–Idaho using the porphyroclast hyperbolic distribution method, and potential use
829 of SC'-type extensional shear bands as quantitative vorticity indicators. *Journal of Structural*
830 *Geology* 30(8), 1005-1012.

831

832 Law, R. D., Knipe, R. J., Dayan, H., 1984. Strain path partitioning within thrust sheets:
833 microstructural and petrofabric evidence from the Moine Thrust zone at Loch Eriboll, northwest
834 Scotland. *Journal of Structural Geology* 6(5), 477-497.

835

836 Law, R.D., Searle, M.P., Simpson, R.L., 2004. Strain, deformation temperatures and vorticity of
837 flow at the top of the Greater Himalayan Slab, Everest Massif, Tibet. *Journal of the Geological*
838 *Society of London* 161, 305-320.

839

840 Little, T.A., Hacker, B.R., Gordon, S.M., Baldwin, S.L., Fitzgerald, P.G., Ellis, S., Korchinski, M.,
841 2011. Diapiric exhumation of the world's youngest (UHP) eclogites in the gneiss domes of the
842 D'Entrecasteaux Islands Papua New Guinea. *Tectonophysics*, 30.

843

- 844 Lister, G. S., Snoke, A. W., 1984. SC mylonites. *Journal of Structural Geology* 6(6), 617-638.
- 845
- 846 Logan, J. M., Dengo, C. A., Higgs, N. G., Wang, Z. Z., 1992. Fabrics of experimental fault zones:
847 Their development and relationship to mechanical behavior. In: Evans, B., Wong, T.F., (Eds.) *Fault*
848 *mechanics and transport properties of rocks*. New York Academic Press, pp. 33-68.
- 849
- 850 Maineri, C., Benvenuti, M., Costagliola, P., Dini, A., Lattanzi, P., Ruggieri, G., Villa, I. M., 2003.
851 Sericitic alteration at the La Crocetta deposit (Elba Island, Italy): interplay between magmatism,
852 tectonics and hydrothermal activity. *Mineralium Deposita* 38(1), 67-86.
- 853
- 854 Massa, G., Musumeci, G., Mazzarini, F., Pieruccioni, D., 2017. Coexistence of contractional and
855 extensional tectonics during the northern Apennines orogeny: the late Miocene out-of-sequence
856 thrust in the Elba Island nappe stack. *Geological Journal* 52(3), 353-368.
- 857
- 858 Massironi, M., Bistacchi, A., Menegon, L., 2011. Misoriented faults in exhumed metamorphic
859 complexes: Rule or exception? *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 307(1), 233-239.
- 860
- 861 Mazzarini, F., Musumeci, G., 2008. Hydrofracturing-related sill and dyke emplacement at shallow
862 crustal levels: the Eastern Elba Dyke Complex, Italy. *Geological Society, London, Special*
863 *Publications* 302(1), 121-129.
- 864
- 865 Means, W.D., 1995. Shear zones and rock history. *Tectonophysics* 247, 157-160.
- 866
- 867 Menegon, L., Pennacchioni, G., Heilbronner, R., Pittarello, L., 2008. Evolution of quartz
868 microstructure and c-axis crystallographic preferred orientation within ductilely deformed
869 granitoids (Arolla unit, Western Alps). *Journal of Structural Geology* 30(11), 1332-1347.

870

871 Menegon, L., Nasipuri, P., Stünitz, H., Behrens, H., & Ravana, E. (2011). Dry and strong quartz
872 during deformation of the lower crust in the presence of melt. *Journal of Geophysical Research:*
873 *Solid Earth* 116(B10).

874

875 Menegon, L., Stünitz, H., Nasipuri, P., Heilbronner, R., Svahnberg, H., 2013. Transition from
876 fracturing to viscous flow in granulite facies perthitic feldspar (Lofoten, Norway). *Journal of*
877 *Structural Geology* 48, 95-112.

878

879 Menegon, L., Pennacchioni, G., Malaspina, N., Harris, K., Wood, E., 2017. Earthquakes as
880 precursors of ductile shear zones in the dry and strong lower crust. *Geochemistry, Geophysics,*
881 *Geosystems*.

882

883 Morris, A., Ferrill, D. A., Henderson, D. B., 1996. Slip-tendency analysis and fault
884 reactivation. *Geology* 24(3), 275-278.

885

886 Musumeci, G., Mazzarini, F., Tiepolo, M., Di Vincenzo, G., 2011. U-Pb and ⁴⁰Ar-³⁹Ar
887 geochronology of Palaeozoic units in the northern Apennines: determining protolith age and alpine
888 evolution using the Calamita Schist and Ortano Porphyroid. *Geological Journal* 46(4), 288-310.

889

890 Musumeci, G., Vaselli, L., 2012. Neogene deformation and granite emplacement in the
891 metamorphic units of northern Apennines (Italy): Insights from mylonitic marbles in the Porto
892 Azzurro pluton contact aureole (Elba Island). *Geosphere* 8(2), 470-490.

893

894 Musumeci, G., Mazzarini, F., Cruden, A. R., 2015. The Zuccale Fault, Elba Island, Italy: a new
895 perspective from fault architecture. *Tectonics* 34(6), 1195-1218.

896

897 Papeschi, S., Musumeci, G., Mazzarini, F., 2017. Heterogeneous brittle-ductile deformation at
898 shallow crustal levels under high thermal conditions: The case of a synkinematic contact aureole in
899 the inner northern Apennines, southeastern Elba Island, Italy. *Tectonophysics* 717, 547-564.

900

901 Passchier, C. W., Trouw, R. A. J., 2005. *Microtectonics*. 2nd Edition. Springer-Verlag, Berlin.

902

903 Passchier, C., Coelho, S., 2006. An outline of shear-sense analysis in high-grade rocks. *Gondwana*
904 *Research* 10(1), 66-76.

905

906 Pattison, D.R.M. Tracy, R.J., 1992. Phase equilibria and thermobarometry of metapelites. In:
907 *Contact Metamorphism* (ed. Kerrick, D.M.), *Reviews in Mineralogy* 26, 105-206.

908

909 Pennacchioni, G., 2005. Control of the geometry of precursor brittle structures on the type of ductile
910 shear zone in the Adamello tonalites, Southern Alps (Italy). *Journal of Structural Geology* 27(4),
911 627-644.

912

913 Pennacchioni, G., Mancktelow, N. S., 2007. Nucleation and initial growth of a shear zone network
914 within compositionally and structurally heterogeneous granitoids under amphibolite facies
915 conditions. *Journal of Structural Geology*, 29(11), 1757-1780.

916

917 Pennacchioni, G., Mancktelow, N. S., 2013. Initiation and growth of strike-slip faults within intact
918 metagranitoid (Neves area, eastern Alps, Italy). *Geological Society of America Bulletin* 125(9-10),
919 1468-1483.

920

- 921 Pertusati, P. C., Raggi, G., Ricci, C. A., Duranti, S., Palmeri, R., 1993. Evoluzione post-collisionale
922 dell'Elba centro-orientale. *Memorie della Società Geologica Italiana* 49, 297-312.
923
- 924 Platt, J.P., 2015. Influence of shear heating on microstructurally defined plate boundary shear
925 zones. *J. Struct. Geol.* 79, 80-89.
926
- 927 Platt, J. P., Vissers, R. L. M., 1980. Extensional structures in anisotropic rocks. *Journal of Structural*
928 *Geology* 2(4), 397-410.
929
- 930 Ponce, C., Druguet, E., Carreras, J., 2013. Development of shear zone-related lozenges in foliated
931 rocks. *Journal of Structural Geology* 50, 176-186.
932
- 933 Ramsay, J. G., 1980. Shear zone geometry: a review. *Journal of structural geology* 2(1-2), 83-99.
934
- 935 Ramsay, J. G., Graham, R. H., 1970. Strain variation in shear belts. *Canadian Journal of Earth*
936 *Sciences* 7(3), 786-813.
937
- 938 Ramsay, J. G., Huber, M. I., 1983. *Techniques of modern structural geology, Volume 1: Strain*
939 *analysis*. Academic Press, London.
940
- 941 Roper, P. J., 1972. Structural significance of "Button" or "Fish Scale" texture in phyllonitic schist
942 of the Brevard Zone, Northwestern South Carolina. *Geological Society of America Bulletin* 83(3),
943 853-860.
944

945 Rosenberg, C. L., Stünitz, H., 2003. Deformation and recrystallization of plagioclase along a
946 temperature gradient: an example from the Bergell tonalite. *Journal of Structural Geology* 25(3),
947 389-408.

948

949 Rutter, E. H., 1986. On the nomenclature of mode of failure transitions in
950 rocks. *Tectonophysics* 122(3-4), 381-387.

951

952 Rutter, E.H., Holdsworth, R.E., Knipe, R., 2001. The nature and tectonic significance of fault-zone
953 weakening: an introduction. *Geol. Soc. Lond. Spec. Publ.* 186, 1-11.

954

955 Schmid, S. M., Handy, M. R., 1991. Towards a genetic classification of fault rocks: geological
956 usage and tectonophysical implications. In: Müller, D.W., McKenzie, J.A., Weissert, H., (Eds.)
957 *Controversies in Modern Geology, evolution of geological theories in sedimentology, earth history*
958 *and tectonics.* Academic Press, London, 339-361.

959

960 Schneider, C. A., Rasband, W. S., & Eliceiri, K. W., 2012. NIH Image to ImageJ: 25 years of image
961 analysis. *Nature methods* 9(7), 671.

962

963 Sibson, R. H., 1977. Fault rocks and fault mechanisms. *Journal of the Geological Society* 133(3),
964 191-213.

965

966 Sibson, R. H., 1983. Continental fault structure and the shallow earthquake source. *Journal of the*
967 *Geological Society* 140(5), 741-767.

968

969 Sibson, R. H., 1985. A note on fault reactivation. *Journal of Structural Geology* 7(6), 751-754.

970

- 971 Simpson, C., De Paor, D. G., 1993. Strain and kinematic analysis in general shear zones. *Journal of*
972 *Structural Geology* 15(1), 1-20.
- 973
- 974 Siivola, J., Schmidt, R., 2007. List of mineral abbreviations. Recommendations by the IUGS
975 Subcommission on the systematics of metamorphic rocks. In: Fettes, D. Desmons, J., (Eds.)
976 *Metamorphic Rocks: A Classification and Glossary of Terms*. Cambridge University Press,
977 Cambridge.
- 978
- 979 Smith, S. A. F., Holdsworth, R. E., Colletini, C., Pearce, M. A., 2011. The microstructural
980 character and mechanical significance of fault rocks associated with a continental low-angle normal
981 fault: the Zuccale Fault, Elba Island, Italy. *Geological Society, London, Special*
982 *Publications* 359(1), 97-113.
- 983
- 984 Steffen, K., Selverstone, J., Brearley, A., 2001. Episodic weakening and strengthening during
985 synmetamorphic deformation in a deep-crustal shear zone in the Alps. *Geol. Soc. Lond. Spec. Publ.*
986 186, 141-156.
- 987
- 988 Stipp, M., Stünitz, H., Heilbronner, R., Schmid, S. M., 2002. The eastern Tonale fault zone: a
989 'natural laboratory' for crystal plastic deformation of quartz over a temperature range from 250 to
990 700 °C. *Journal of Structural Geology* 24(12), 1861-1884.
- 991
- 992 Stipp, M., Tullis, J., Scherwath, M., Behrmann, J. H., 2010. A new perspective on paleopiezometry:
993 Dynamically recrystallized grain size distributions indicate mechanism changes. *Geology* 38(8),
994 759-762.
- 995

- 996 Stünitz, H., & Tullis, J., 2001. Weakening and strain localization produced by syn-deformational
997 reaction of plagioclase. *International Journal of Earth Sciences* 90(1), 136-148.
998
- 999 Tanaka, H., 1992. Cataclastic lineations. *Journal of Structural Geology* 14, 1239-1252.
1000
- 1001 Trevisan, L. (1950). *L'Elba orientale e la sua tettonica di scivolamento per gravità*. Società
1002 Cooperativa Tipografica, Padova.
1003
- 1004 Tullis, J., Snoke, A. W., Todd, V. R., 1982. Significance and petrogenesis of mylonitic
1005 rocks. *Geology* 10(5), 227-230.
1006
- 1007 Viegas, G., Menegon, L., Archanjo, C., 2016. Brittle grain-size reduction of feldspar, phase mixing
1008 and strain localization in granitoids at mid-crustal conditions (Pernambuco shear zone, NE
1009 Brazil). *Solid Earth* 7(2), 375-396.
1010
- 1011 Voll, G., 1976. Recrystallization of quartz, biotite and feldspars from Erstfeld to the Leventina
1012 Nappe, Swiss Alps, and its geological significance. *Schweiz. Mineral. Petrogr. Mitt.* 56, 147.
1013
- 1014 Wallis, S., 1995. Vorticity analysis and recognition of ductile extension in the Sanbagawa belt, SW
1015 Japan. *Journal of Structural Geology* 17(8), 1077-1093.
1016
- 1017 White, S., 1979. Large strain deformation: report on a Tectonic Studies Group discussion meeting
1018 held at Imperial College, London on 14 November 1979. *Journal of Structural Geology* 1(4), 333-
1019 339.
1020

- 1021 White, S. H., Burrows, S. E., Carreras, J., Shaw, N. D., Humphreys, F. J., 1980. On mylonites in
1022 ductile shear zones. *Journal of Structural Geology* 2(1-2), 175-187.
- 1023
- 1024 Zhang, L., He, C., 2016. Frictional properties of phyllosilicate-rich mylonite and conditions for the
1025 brittle-ductile transition. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth* 121(4), 3017-3047.

Table 1

Calculated mean attitude of structural elements and shear band geometries at the meso- and the microscale. Errors at 1σ . Details of the statistical parameters of Fisher mean vectors are provided in Appendix A.

Capo Calvo	
Structural element	Mean (1σ)
Sp	240.9/57.2±12.0°
C'	242.5/57.1±12.8°
Lp	78.4/28.4±15.7°
Praticciolo	
Sm	79.2/56.9±15.1°
C'	70.5/87.1±9.1°
C' – antithetic	47.3/18.2±39.5°
Sm/C' dihedral angle	30.2±8.8°
Sm/C' antithetic dihedral angle	134.6±21.2°
C'/C' antithetic dihedral angle	110.9±20.3°
Lp	254.6/32.0±15.9°
Microscale	
sample • dihedral angle	Mean (1σ)
SP196 • Sp/C'	41.9±4.6°
• Sp/C	21.1±4.6°
• C/C'	15.2±1.9°
SP196 (lozenge subset) • S/C	36.7±2.4°
SP196 (contact subset) • S/C	21.1±3.5°
CS30 • Sm/C'	38.4±3.7°
SP65 • Sm/C'	34.8±3.4°
• Sm/C' - antithetic	142.8±10.0°
SP76 • Sm/C'	35.3±3.1°
• Sm/C' - antithetic	144.0±9.2°
SP78 • Sm/C'	31.2±3.1°
• Sm/C' - antithetic	144.6±1.2°

Capo Calvo

Praticciolo

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Highlights

- Shear zones evolved during temperature decrease in the Calamita Schists aureole.
- Networks of low grade shear bands overprint an earlier high grade foliation.
- Mylonitic shear zones are produced by passively rotating the pre existing high grade foliation.
- C'-type shear bands nucleate due to localized embrittlement of coarse quartz boudins.
- Brittle structures reactivate pre-existing shear bands producing an array of low angle brittle faults.